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Research Article

Understanding the Knowledge, Attitude and Awareness of the Public Towards Liver Disease in Tumkur Region

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ABSTRACT

The liver is the largest internal organ vital for metabolism, detoxification nutrient storage, and bile production. Common liver diseases include hepatitis, fatty liver disease (alcoholic and non- alcoholic), cirrhosis and liver cancer. Liver disease arises from alcohol, viruses, fat build-up or genetics. The present study was planned to assess Knowledge, attitude and awareness among liver disease participants. To assess Knowledge, Attitude and Awareness among Liver Disease participants. A cross-sectional observational study was undertaken for a three-month period, Data of our study was collected on the basis of Knowledge, Attitude Questionnaires. A total number of 260 participants in Tumkur region, 150 were selected as community basis and 110 were selected on college basis. In community basis 61 participants were aged about 18-28 shows 40.66% major respondents. In college basis 80 participants were aged about 18-20 shows 72.72%. They are also distributed social habits like 5.7% were smokers & 11.5% were both smokers and alcoholic. Through this study we concluded that among community basis and college basis, the college basis has better knowledge. The clinical pharmacist plays a crucial role in educating the patients regarding disease and drugs. The study highlights the need for conducting awareness programme regards life style modification and liver disease management among the participants.

INTRODUCTION

Chronic liver disease (CLD):

It is defined as a progressive decline in liver function lasting more than six months, affecting

the synthesis of clotting factors and other essential proteins, the detoxification of harmful metabolic substances, and the excretion of bile.

CLD is a continuous process involving inflammation, damage, and regeneration of the

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liver parenchyma, ultimately resulting in fibrosis and cirrhosis.^[1]

Cirrhosis and its complications are becoming a leading cause of death in India, according to current data. Cirrhosis and liver cancer are mostly caused by hepatitis B and C, as well as alcoholic and non-alcoholic liver diseases.

Managing these conditions presents numerous challenges, including limited resources, a lack of hepatologists and healthcare facilities, cultural differences, reliance on untested and unproven traditional medicines and herbal supplements, a lack of universal education and awareness of disease transmission, and a higher prevalence of poverty and malnutrition.^[2]

Types of Liver Disease:

1. Fatty liver disease
 - a. Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease
 - b. Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease
2. Viral hepatitis
 - a. Hepatitis A
 - b. Hepatitis B
 - c. Hepatitis C
 - d. Hepatitis D
 - e. Hepatitis E
3. Autoimmune hepatitis
4. Cirrhosis
5. Fibrosis

ALCOHOLIC FATTY LIVER DISEASE [AFLD]:^[3]

It refers to a group of conditions that begin with fatty liver, proceed to alcoholic hepatitis, and eventually leads to alcoholic cirrhosis, the most

severe and permanent form of liver destruction caused by alcohol consumption.

There are three histologic phases of alcoholic liver disease

- Alcoholic Fatty Liver
- Alcoholic Hepatitis
- Alcoholic Cirrhosis

Etiology: Alcohol abuse, Alcoholic cirrhosis, Viral hepatitis, Obesity, High fat diet, Histological damage.

Signs and Symptoms: Nausea and vomiting, Abdominal pain, Loss of appetite, Increased thirst, Yellowish of eyes, Weakness, Fever, Confusion, Mood swings.

Diagnosis: Physical examination, Laboratory tests, Liver biopsy, Emphysema, Alpha-1 antitrypsin deficiency, Ascending cholangitis.

Treatment:

Pharmacological treatment

- Acamprosate
- Naltrexone
- Disulfiram

Non-Pharmacological treatment

- Cessation of alcohol consumption
- Nutritional support
- Weight management
- Smoking cessation
- Psychosocial support

Fig 01: Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease

NON-ALCOHOLIC FATTY LIVER DISEASE [NAFLD]:

- NAFLD is defined as hepatic steatosis occurring without excessive alcohol intake and without any other underlying chronic liver disease.
- Although NAFLD is now one of the leading causes of chronic liver disease worldwide, public awareness about the condition remains very low.
- NAFLD has rapidly increased in Western countries, reaching a global prevalence of 25%.^[4]

Etiology: Obesity, Type 2 diabetes mellitus, Dyslipidaemias, Metabolic syndrome, Genetic inheritance, Side effects of medications.

Signs and Symptoms: Nausea, Vomiting, Jaundice, Pruritis, Memory impairment, Loss of appetite, Gynecomastia

Diagnosis: Clinical evaluation, Imaging, Laboratory tests, sometimes liver biopsy^[5]

Treatment:

Pharmacological treatment

- Pioglitazone in patients with biopsy-proven 30-45mg/day
- Vitamin E in nondiabetic adults with NASH without cirrhosis 800IU/day

Non-Pharmacological treatment

- Reduce calorie intake by 500-1000kcal/day
- Physical activity 150-200min/week^[6]

Fig 02: Non- Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease

Aim and Objectives:

Aim:

A study to assess the Knowledge, Attitude and Awareness regarding Liver Disease in Tumkur region.

Objectives:

- To evaluate the socio-demographic characteristics of respondents.
- To assess the knowledge and awareness of respondents.
- To assess the attitude of respondents related to prevention of liver disease.
- To analyse the prevalence of liver disease among the participants.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study Site:

The study will be carried out in community of Tumkur region.

Duration of Study:

The study will be undertaken for a three-month period.

Study Design:

A cross-sectional observational study.

Proposed Sample size:

260

Source of Data:

- a. Direct interact with participants
- b. Patients case sheet

Study Criteria:

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Participants age more than 18 years.• Both the gender.• Patient diagnosed with or without liver disease.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Age below 18 years.• Special population (pregnancy and lactating women)

Study Procedure:

- Regarding this project pilot study has been done.
- Collected the review of literature pertaining to the project.
- Prepared the study protocol including study design and design of perform.
- Enrolled the participants according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria.
- Taken a patient consent.
- Collected the participants details from the direct interaction with patient and patient case sheet.
- Assessed the knowledge, attitude and awareness with the help of questionnaire.
- Provided the counselling to the patient.
- Provided patient information leaflets.
- The obtained information was analysed and represented in the form of table and graphs and data were analysed statistically.
- Submission of report.

Material Used:

- Informed consent form.
- Knowledge Attitude questionnaires
- PIL (Patient information leaflet)

Methods:

- Data were collected from patient documents.
- The medical history consisting of in-patient, medical, records was reviewed.

- Data was recorded as patient demographic information, clinical status, duration of disease and type of complication.

rural basis [77(51.33%) were males and 73(48.66%) were females] and 110 participants are selected on college basis [33(30%) were males and 77(70%) were females].

RESULTS:

A three-month cross-sectional observational study was conducted among chronic liver disease participants from rural and college setting in the Tumkur region. A total number of 260 participants are participated during the study period. Out of 260 participants 150 participants are selected on

Distribution of participants according to gender on rural basis:

Gender	Total no. of participants(N=150)	Percentage
Male	77	51.33%
Female	73	48.66%

Distribution of participants according to gender on college basis:

Gender	Total no. of participants(N=110)	Percentage
Male	33	30%
Female	77	70%

Distribution of participants according to age groups on rural basis:

Among 150 rural-based participants, age ranges from 18 years to participants above 50 years. They

are categorised into 4 groups, among these groups majority of the participants were from age range 18-28 years i.e., 61 participants (40.66%) and only 25 participants (16.66%) were from age between 40-50 years.

Age (years)	No. of participants (N=150)	Percentage
18-28	61	40.66%
29-39	37	24.66%
40-50	25	16.66%
51 & above	27	18%

Distribution of participants according to age group on college basis:

Among 110 college-based participants, age ranges from 18 years to 28 years. They are categorised into 2 groups, among these majority of the participants were from age range 18-20 years i.e.,

80 participants (72.72%) and 30 participants (27.27%) were from age range between 21-28 years.

Age (years)	No. of participants (N=110)	Percentage
18-20	80	72.72%
21-28	30	27.27%

Distribution of participants based on social history:

Distribution of 260 participants based on social history was in 3 categories namely Smoker, Smoker and Alcoholic, and Alcoholic. Among 260 participants, 190 (73.07%) were neither smokers

nor alcoholics and 30 (11.53%) were found to be smokers and alcoholics.

Category	No. of participants (N=260)	Percentage
Smoker	15	5.76%
Smoker & Alcoholic	30	11.53%
Alcoholic	25	9.61%
Nil	190	73.07%

Assessment of Knowledge:

Among 260 participants, in Assessment of Knowledge based Questionnaires majority of the participants showed [YES] response for Drinking

too much alcohol can cause AFLD? (73.07%) and only (19.23%) of participants showed [YES] response for Do you think you are at risk of NAFLD?

SR. NO	Questions	% of Yes response	% of No response	% of Don't know response
1	Have you heard about NAFLD before today?	48.84%	45.76%	5.38%
2	Abdominal pain is a common symptom of NAFLD?	56.93%	20%	23.07%
3	Yellow pigmentation of skin and eyes (jaundice) is a common symptom of AFLD?	48.07%	27.69%	24.23%
4	Drinking too much alcohol can cause AFLD?	73.07%	17.30%	9.61%
5	Eating too much added sugar can cause NAFLD?	45%	28.07%	26.92%
6	Eating too much fat can cause AFLD?	48.84%	33.07%	18.07%
7	Being obese or overweight is a risk factor for NAFLD?	53.84%	22.30%	23.84%
8	Smoking is the risk factor for NAFLD?	47.69%	22.84%	23.46%
9	Do you think NAFLD can have dangerous conditions?	56.53%	20.38%	23.07%
10	Do you think you are at a risk of NAFLD?	19.23%	55%	25.76%

Assessment of Attitude:

Among 260 participants, in Assessment of Attitude based Questionnaires majority the of

participants showed [YES] response for Do you think obesity cause NAFLD? (57.30%) and only (28.84%) participants showed [YES] response for Do you think hypertension affects NAFLD?

SR. NO	Questions	% of Yes response	% of No response	% of Don't know response
1	Would you undergo for medical screening for NAFLD?	34.23%	50%	15.76%
2	Do you think obesity cause NAFLD?	57.30%	24.23%	18.46%
3	Do you think diabetes cause NAFLD?	43.07%	30%	26.92%
4	Do you think high level of cholesterol cause NAFLD?	53.07%	30.76%	16.15%
5	Do you think hypertension affects NAFLD?	28.84%	33.46%	37.69%
6	Do you think exercise affect the avoidance of NAFLD?	53.84%	5.38%	20.76%
7	Do you think exercise affects the avoidance of NAFLD?	48.07%	25.38%	26.53%
8	Do you think people with chronic liver disease feel about having disease?	42.69%	23.07%	34.23%
9	Do you refer patients of NAFLD gastroenterologist?	35%	30%	35%
10	Do you think NAFLD major health problem?	55.38%	19.61%	25%

Comparison of YES response between Assessment of Knowledge & Attitude Questionnaires:

YES, response is compared between both Assessment of Knowledge and Assessment of

Attitude Questionnaires. In these 49.04% participants showed response for Assessment of Knowledge Questionnaire and only 45.49% participants showed response for Assessment of Attitude Questionnaires.

DISCUSSION:

Liver disease, particularly alcoholic fatty liver disease (AFLD) and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), has become a major global health burden. AFLD is mainly associated with chronic alcohol consumption, whereas NAFLD is closely linked to lifestyle factors such as obesity, unhealthy diet, and physical inactivity. The increasing prevalence of NAFLD, even among younger individuals, is a growing concern. Treatment approaches for these conditions are divided into pharmacological and non-pharmacological strategies. Although drug

therapies are being developed, lifestyle modification through diet control, weight management, and regular exercise remains the most effective and sustainable option. Integrating modern medical therapies with traditional practices, including Nutraceuticals and Ayurveda, may offer new opportunities for holistic management.

Knowledge, Attitude, and Awareness (KAA) studies help to assess how well a population understands a health condition, their attitudes towards it, and their practices in managing it. In the context of liver disease, such studies guide

healthcare professionals and policymakers in designing effective interventions and educational programs. A cross-sectional observational study was conducted in Tumkur region with 260 participants. Out 260 participants majority participants showed that 73.07% recognized alcohol as cause of AFLD, but only 19.23% felt at risk for NAFLD for Assessment of Knowledge bases Questionnaires and 57.30% recognized obesity can cause NAFLD, but only 28.84% participants think hypertension affects NAFLD. Although many participants understood symptoms and the importance of checkups, adherence to regular medication and monitoring was still low.

CONCLUSION

Liver disease is a significant and growing public health challenge worldwide, affecting millions of people due to both alcoholic and non-alcoholic causes. It often progresses from simple fatty liver to advanced stages such as cirrhosis and liver failure, emphasizing the importance of early detection and timely treatment. Life style modification, including a healthy diet, regular physical activity, reduced alcohol consumption, and proper weight management, remains the cornerstone of prevention. Public health initiatives, patient education, and access to appropriate medical care also play a vital role in reducing the overall disease burden. By integrating clinical advances with community-level awareness programs, better health outcomes can be achieved for individuals at risk or already affected. Clinical pharmacist plays a crucial role in guiding patients about liver disease, medication safety, and lifestyle practices, making patient education an essential part comprehensive care. Bad adopting a healthy lifestyle, people can significantly reduce their risk of developing liver diseases and maintain overall well-being. In the

Tumkur region, understanding the public's knowledge, attitude, and awareness towards liver disease is essential for designing effective health strategies. Assessing these factors helps identify gaps in awareness, misconceptions, and preventive practices. Enhancing community education in Tumkur can empower individual to recognize early symptoms, seek timely care, and adopt healthier behaviours.

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